

Do Constraints Increase Creativity More Than Freedom?

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April 2026

1 ABSTRACT

Does limiting choice actually make us more creative? This study explores whether constraints can outperform freedom in the idea of generation through a short experiment comparing free thinking and constrained thinking, the results suggest that constraints may improve the quality and practicality of ideas while freedom has more of creativity in different ways.

2 INTRODUCTION

Creativity is typically defined as the ability to generate ideas by exploring. This process relates to Divergent thinking, where individuals explore many possibilities for a single problem. However, real-world problem-solving often requires narrowing down ideas using Convergent thinking, where the individual focuses on identifying the single best solution for a problem.

This study explores a key question! Do constraints enhance creativity by forcing more focused thinking, or do they limit the idea generation?

3 METHODOLOGY

A simple experiment was conducted using the problem: "How can students reduce phone usage?"

Two rounds were performed using Divergent thinking and convergent thinking:

Round 1:

No constraints were applied. 7 ideas were generated in 7 minutes

→ setting limits on apps (3/5)

→ Creating phone free zones (3/5)

→ replacing screen time with hobbies (5/5)

→ Exploring places near them (4/5)

- spending time with friends (5/5)
- reading books (5/5)
- Practice meditation or do exercises (2/5)

Round 2:

The same problem was approached with the following constraints:

1. No money
2. No apps or technology use
3. Must be implemented in less than 5 minutes

7 ideas were generated in 7 minutes

- Creating physical distance (2/5)
- Ban phone while waking, waiting, etc. (3/5)
- Delete social media (5/5)
- think for 10 seconds before touching the phone (2/5)
- Carry a sketchpad (5/5)
- workout (4/5)
- start studying for 10 minutes (5/5)

After generation, the top 3 ideas from each round were selected and evaluated based on:

originality and practical application.

Top three from the round 1 are,

1. Spending time with friends
2. replacing screentime with hobbies
3. reading books

Top three from the round 2 are :

1. Deleting Social media
- 2 Carrying a sketch pad
3. start studying for 10 minutes

4 RESULTS

The free-thinking round produced a larger variety of ideas, but many were good, not practically useful. In contrast, the constrained round produced a fewer but more specific ideas which are practical. So on average:

The constrained ideas scored higher in usefulness. Free ideas showed slightly higher variety but Lower clarity.

5 DISCUSSION

The findings suggests that constraints leads to more actionable and practicality useful solutions while free thinking leads to more variety of solutions which may or may not leads to practicality useful solutions.

Constraints act as a filter during idea generation, encouraging focus and forcing the brain tow work within defined boundaries. This balance between

exploration and limitation reflects the interaction between Divergent and Convergent thinking.

6 CONCLUSION

This study concludes that constraints do not necessarily reduce creativity. Instead, they can enhance the quality and applicability of ideas, even if they reduce the total number of ideas generated.

Therefore, creativity may not depend solely on freedom, but on how effectively limitations are used to guide thinking.

7 FUTURE SCOPE

Future research could explore how different types of constraints impact creativity across domains